

Acute and Sub acute Toxicity Studies of *Euphorbia hirta* on Mice and Wistar rats

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ABSTRACT: This study aimed at evaluating the acute and subacute toxicity of the aqueous leaf extract of *Euphorbia hirta* in experimental animals. For acute toxicity assessment, mice were orally administered single doses of 2000 and 3000 mg/kg body weight (bw), with the administration volume set at 1 mL/100 g bw. A limit test was conducted to estimate the median lethal dose (LD₅₀). In the subacute toxicity study, rats received daily oral doses of 500, 1000, 2000 and 3000 mg/kg bw for 28 consecutive days. A control group received distilled water. Biochemical parameters including alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), Alanine phosphatase (ALP), Total protein, creatinine and Urea were analyzed in plasma samples. Hematological parameters such as red and white blood cell counts, hemoglobin, hematocrit and platelets were also evaluated. Histopathological examination of the liver and kidneys was performed to assess organ-specific toxicity. The results indicated that the LD₅₀ of the aqueous extract of *Euphorbia hirta* is greater than 3000 mg/kg, suggesting low acute toxicity. In the subacute study, histological examination of rat organs revealed no acute or chronic damage, although minor liver changes such as sinusoidal dilatation and mild portal inflammation were observed at high doses which is supported with elevated AST and ALT. In conclusion, the toxicological profile indicates that these extracts are safe at tested doses, although higher concentrations may warrant caution due to mild histological and biochemical changes.

KEY WORDS: *Euphorbia hirta*, Toxicity, mice and wistar rats

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Toxicity refers to the capacity of a substance to cause harm to living organisms and is a fundamental consideration in pharmacological and biomedical research (1). This is especially important in the evaluation of drugs, chemicals, and natural products, including medicinal plant extracts. Although many plants are traditionally recognized for their therapeutic benefits, they may also harbor bioactive compounds that can exert adverse effects when consumed at high doses or over prolonged periods (2). As such, establishing the toxicological profile of any medicinal substance is essential to ensure its safety for human and animal use (1,3). Toxicological assessments are conducted to identify harmful effects on specific organs, physiological systems, or the entire organism. These assessments encompass acute, subacute, subchronic, and chronic studies, as well as evaluations of genotoxicity, reproductive toxicity, and hepatotoxicity. Findings from such studies help determine safe dosage ranges, identify potential side effects, and elucidate mechanisms of toxicity (4). In the field of herbal medicine, toxicity studies serve a vital role in bridging traditional usage with modern scientific validation. Many medicinal plants, despite their longstanding use, lack comprehensive safety data. Without proper toxicological evaluation, the risk of inappropriate usage increases, potentially leading to serious health consequences (5) Therefore, toxicity testing is indispensable in the development of safe, effective, and standardized herbal remedies (6). One such medicinal plant is *Euphorbia hirta*, commonly referred to as the asthma plant or "Tawa-Tawa." A member of the Euphorbiaceae family, it is widely distributed across tropical and subtropical regions and commonly grows along roadsides, farmlands, and grasslands. Traditionally, *Euphorbia hirta* has been used in the treatment of numerous ailments, including asthma, cough, diarrhea, dysentery, skin infections, and fever (6,7). Its pharmacological activities such as antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antidiarrheal, antioxidant, and antiasthmatic effects are attributed to its rich phytochemical content, which includes flavonoids,

alkaloids, tannins, saponins, and phenolic compounds (8). Despite its widespread medicinal use, there are conflicting opinions regarding its safety (8). These concerns highlight the urgent need for comprehensive toxicological evaluations, especially given the plant's increasing popularity and potential integration into modern phytotherapeutic products.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Plant Collection, Authentication and Pulverization of the Plant Leaves

Fresh leaves of *Euphorbia hirta* were collected from Kwara State stadium Ilorin, Nigeria. The plants were identified and authenticated at the herbarium unit of the Department of plant biology, Faculty of life sciences, University of Ilorin, Kwara State, where they were given the herbarium voucher number UILH/001/1511/2024. Leaves of *Euphorbia hirta* were washed thoroughly and air dried in shade for two weeks. Dried leaves were ground into a fine powder using an industrial blender.

2.1.1 Preparation of Aqueous Extracts

A total of 100 g e of air-dried, ground leaves of *Euphorbia hirta* were accurately weighed and soaked separately in 250 ml of distilled water in sterile conical flasks. The mixtures were covered and allowed to stand for 72 hours at room temperature (approximately 25 ± 2 °C) with occasional stirring to facilitate the release of bioactive constituents. After maceration, the mixtures were filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper to remove plant debris. The aqueous filtrates were then subjected to lyophilization (freeze-drying), a technique widely recognized for preserving thermolabile compounds and improving extract stability and shelf life. Prior to lyophilization, the filtrates were pre-frozen at -20 °C for 24 hours to ensure solidification. The frozen samples were then transferred to a freeze-dryer and processed under vacuum at a condenser temperature of approximately -50 °C and chamber pressure of ≤ 0.133 mBar. The drying cycle continued for 48–72 hours until complete sublimation of water content was achieved, resulting in a dry, powdery extract. The lyophilized extracts were carefully collected, weighed, and stored in airtight amber containers at 4 °C until further use in toxicological and phytochemical evaluations (9,10).

2.1.2 Percentage yield of *Euphorbia hirta*

Formula;

$$\frac{\text{Weight of Extract (g)} \times 100}{\text{Weight of plant (g)}} \quad (11).$$

Aqueous: $\frac{5.2}{100} \times 100 = 5.2\%$

2.2 Acute toxicity study

A total number of 15 mice of 8 weeks old were grouped into 3 i.e Group 1 - 3 in which each group contained five healthy adult mice of 30-35g/bw. Animal were allowed to acclimatize to the laboratory condition for one week given water and food. After seven days, animals were kept on fasting overnight. Group 2 and 3 were given 2000 and 3000mg/kg of aqueous extract of *Euphorbia hirta* (AEE) respectively while control (Group 1) received distilled water with the administer dose volume of 1ml/100g bw via an oral route by gavage using a suitable intubation cannula and were subjected to observation for 48hrs. All the animals were observed for any signs of physical and behavioral alterations for 14 days (12).

Table 1: Protocol table for acute toxicity study of *Euphorbia hirta*

Groups administered (ml/bw)	Number of mice	Extract type	Dose mg/kg	Volume
1	5	Water	-	1 ml/100g
2	5	AEE	2000	1 ml/100g
3	5	AEE	3000	1 ml/100g

Key: AEE: Aqueous extract of *Euphorbia hirta*

2.3 Sub acute toxicity study

Twenty wister rats were divided into control and 4 groups of four. Once randomized, the rats received the aqueous extracts of *Euphorbia hirta* (AEE) leaves orally for 28 days. Control group received 1ml/bw of distilled water. Groups 1 received *Euphorbia hirta* (AEE) at 500mg/kg. Group 2,3 and 4 received at 1000,2000 and 3000mg/kg respectively. During the experimental period, body weight, food and water consumption were evaluated once a week. At the end of the experiments all animals of all groups were sacrificed. The animals were made unconscious with chloroform inhalation (cotton wool soaked in 3.5% chloroform) and blood was collected via cardiac puncture using a 5-ml syringe attached to a needle. The blood samples were collected in two different bottles: The (EDTA) for hematological analyzes and lithium heparin bottles for (biochemical tests).The blood collected in lithium heparin were centrifuged at 3600 rpm for fifteen minutes. The collected plasma was stored at -20 ° C until used. Enzyme kits and codes used are among others Cypress diagnostics kits code HBE07 (ALT), Cypress diagnostics kits code HBE06 (AST), Fortress diagnostics kits code BXC0193 (TB) and Fortress diagnostics kits code BXC0184 (ALP) (12). The analysis of the various hematological parameters and biochemical parameters and histological examination were carried out in the University of Ilorin Teaching Hospital Laboratories. The histological examination was carried out on the liver and kidneys of rats treated with the highest dose of plant extract (2000 and 3000 mg/kg).

Table 2: Protocol table for subacute toxicity

Group	Number of rats	Extracts	Dose(mg/kg)	Remarks
Control	4	Distilled water	0	-
1	4	AEE	500	Low
2	4	AEE	1000	Medium
3	4	AEE	2000	High
4	4	AEE	3000	Very high

Key: AEE: aqueous extract of *Euphorbia hirta*

2.4 Preparation of Tissue Sections

After four weeks of the experiment, the animals were euthanized and the livers and Kidneys were removed and fixed immediately in 10% formal saline for 48 hours. Thin slices were cut from each sample, put in tissue cassettes and labeled appropriately; they were processed using paraffin wax tissues processing method as follows:

The tissues were dehydrated in ascending grades (70%, 80%, 90% and absolute) of alcohol, with a timing of 2 hours each and allowed to stay overnight in the absolute alcohol, cleared in two changes of xylene, with a timing of 1 hour each, with infiltration and impregnation in two changes of paraffin wax with a timing of 1 hour each. After tissue processing, the tissues were embedded in molten paraffin wax, cooled rapidly on ice and ribbon sections of the tissue were cut with a LEICA RM 2135RT rotary microtome at three (3) microns. The sections were floated and attached to the slide with the aid of the floating fluid (20% alcohol) and floating bath. The attached sections on the slides were then labeled with the corresponding number on the tissue cassettes. The slides were then dried at 65°C in a hot air oven to allow for proper attachment of the section (13).

2.4.1 Staining TechniquesHaematoxylin and Eosin

The reagents used in this process were: Haematoxylin (Primary stain), eosin (Counter stain).The cut sections were de-waxed in xylene for one hour, hydrated in descending grades of alcohol (absolute alcohol — 70% alcohol), rinsed in water, stained with Haematoxylin for 15minutes, rinsed in water, differentiate in 1% acid alcohol briefly, blued in running tap water for 10 minutes, and stained with Eosin for 2 minutes. It was dehydrated in ascending grades of alcohol (70% alcohol — absolute alcohol), cleared in xylene then mounted with DibutylPhthalate Xylene (DPX) (13).

2.4.2 Photomicrographs

The slides were examined under the microscope at a low power objective (X10) and photomicrographs were taken, slides with pathological lesions were also examined at high power (X40) objective and photomicrographs were also taken at that objective for better magnification (13,14).

3.0 RESULTS

Fig 1: Graph showing the weight of wistar rats before and after exposure to the extracts

Fig 2: Bar chart showing the weight of the organs of the wistar rats.

Fig 3: Biochemical parameters of *Euphobiahirta* aqueous and methanol extracts on wistar rats

Fig 4: Hematological parameters of *Euphobia hirta* aqueous extracts on wistar rats

Fig5. CONTROL KIDNEY

Fig6. GROUP 3 KIDNEY

Fig7. GROUP 4 KIDNEY

Fig8. CONTROL LIVER

Fig9. GROUP 3 LIVER

Fig10. GROUP 4 LIVER

Fig 5-10: Photomicrograph showing the histology of livers and kidneys of wistar rats

4.0 DISCUSSION

The present study evaluated the acute and subacute toxicity profile of *Euphorbia hirta* aqueous leaf extract in rodents, with results indicating a high margin of safety. No mortality or behavioral abnormalities were observed in animals administered single oral doses of 2000 and 3000 mg/kg. According to the Globally Harmonized System (GHS) for the classification of chemicals and the criteria proposed by (15,16), substances with oral LD₅₀ values between 5000 and 15,000 mg/kg are regarded as practically non-toxic. This finding is consistent with reports by (17), who demonstrated that hydroethanolic *Euphorbia hirta* extract exhibited an LD₅₀ greater than 18.5 g/kg in mice, indicating low acute toxicity (18). During the 28-day subacute toxicity assessment, animals treated with 500, 1000, 2000 and 3000 mg/kg/day of the extract did not exhibit signs of behavioral distress or alterations in weight gain, suggesting the extract does not adversely affect general metabolism or appetite. This is in agreement with the findings of (16,19), who reported no significant deviations in body weight or behavioral changes in rats treated with *Euphorbia hirta* extracts for subacute durations. Toxicological indicators such as body and organ weight reductions are commonly associated with systemic toxicity and organ dysfunction (20). The absence of such changes in this study supports the relative non-toxicity of the extract. Hematological analysis revealed no evidence of anemia, leukopenia, or thrombocytopenia, suggesting the extract does not suppress bone marrow function or cause hemolysis. These findings are comparable to those of (21), who found no significant hematological toxicity in rats administered with other medicinal extracts, further indicating hematopoietic safety (23). The liver and kidneys are critical for xenobiotic metabolism and detoxification. Serum biochemical parameters such as ALT, AST, ALP, creatinine, and total bilirubin are widely accepted biomarkers for assessing hepatic and renal integrity (24). In this study, animals administered low and moderate doses of *Euphorbia hirta* extract showed no significant deviations in these parameters. However, mild elevations in ALT and AST were observed in animals exposed to the highest dose (3000 mg/kg), suggesting a potential for hepatic stress at elevated concentrations. This observation aligns with the work of (25), who reported similar increases in liver enzymes following administration of high doses of *Euphorbia hirta* extract. Histopathological evaluations revealed preservation of normal architecture in liver and kidney tissues across most treatment groups. However, at high doses, minor hepatic changes such as sinusoidal dilatation and mild portal inflammation were noted. While these changes were not extensive or indicative of overt hepatotoxicity, they correlate with the biochemical elevations in transaminases and suggest a dose-dependent hepatic effect. Similar histological findings were documented by (26), who observed mild structural changes in hepatic tissues at elevated doses of *Euphorbia hirta* extract (27). Although *Euphorbia hirta* leaf extract appears safe at therapeutic doses, caution may be necessary when used in high concentrations or for prolonged periods. In contrast, hepatotoxic effects have been more pronounced with certain other *Euphorbia* species or formulations, particularly those containing high levels of anthraquinones. For example, case reports of senna-induced cholestatic hepatitis have been documented in elderly individuals using senna-containing laxatives (28).

CONCLUSION

The aqueous leaf extract of *Euphorbia hirta* demonstrates a favorable safety profile in both acute and subacute toxicity evaluations. It is practically non-toxic by oral administration and does not significantly impact hematological, hepatic, or renal function at doses up to 1000 mg/kg. However, the mild hepatic changes observed at higher doses warrant further investigation, especially for long-term use. These findings support the ethnomedicinal use of *Euphorbia hirta* but highlight the importance of dose regulation and continuous safety monitoring.

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